

Role of Visual Resources in Teaching and Learning among Basic Five Learners at Kyebi Presbyterian Basic School in the Ashanti Region of Ghana

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Abstract: The focus of the study was to explore the roles of the visual resources in the teaching and learning at the Kyebi Presbyterian Basic School. The study adopted the qualitative method of research design. The population of the study consisted of the learners and teachers in the school, who were randomly and purposively sampled respectively. Data was collected using questionnaire, interview as well as observation. The data was analyzed using thematic content analysis approach. It was revealed that, visual resources are the tangible objects that could be seen and touched. The study made it clear that, visual resources help learners to relate abstract objects to reality during teaching and learning situation. Also, the visual resources help to arouse the interest of the learners. It was therefore recommended that, the Sekyere Central District Assembly should encourage the study of visual Arts in their schools so as to harness the full potentials of the learners in the Visual Arts. Furthermore, the use of teaching learning resources should be strengthened in Kyebi Presbyterian Primary school to help teaching and learning to be more friendly and interesting.

Keywords: Visual Resources, Creative Works, Performing arts, Teaching, Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background to the study

Visual arts play critical role in the lives of the people of Ghana. In all daily transactions of Ghanaian, visual resources are seen playing roles in worship, chieftaincy, and festivals. And in educational establishments, visual resources are always seen dominating.

According to Walden et al (2021), Visual arts are helpful in Ghanaian society; because they serve as communicative medium as well as for preservation of history and culture. They opine that, the Visual resources are equally used for decorations or adornment purposes. During the teaching and learning situations as well, one is likely to see drawings, paintings and sculpture in various forms. All these are manifestations and testimonies that visual arts and human society depend on each other.

According to Ndah et al (2021), Art and the related works are part of Ghanaian society; as they are seen through the life cycle events of Ghanaian. They collaborate that, the Art works could manifest in three forms namely, Verbal, Visual and the Performing arts.

Kyebi Primary school where the study is targeted is surrounded with many artifacts around the school environment and inside the classrooms. No wonder, Arthur (2009) explains that the arts are good phenomena to be involved in the teaching and learning because they help to translate abstract concepts into reality for the understanding of the learners.

Statement of the problem

Ghanaian society is associated with many artifacts both tangible and intangible In Kyebi community in the Sekyere Central District of the Asante Region in Ghana as well, artifacts are dominant. But observation has shown that, much empirical studies have not been carried out to unearth the roles of the visual resources in the teaching and learning in the area. It is as a result of this that this study is done to discuss the creative works that could be classified under the visual resources, roles of the visual resources in teaching and learning as well as outlining various means through which visual arts could be sustained among the students of Kyebi Primary School.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Discuss the Creative works that fall under the Visual resources.
2. Explain the role of Visual Arts in the Teaching and Learning at Kyebi Primary school.
3. Outline various means by which Visual Resources could be sustained among the students of Kyebi Primary School.

Research questions

1. What are the Creative works that fall under the Visual Resources?
2. What are the roles of Visual Arts in teaching and learning at Kyebi Primary School?
3. What are some of the means by which Visual Arts could be sustained at Kyebi Primary School?

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The following sub topics are reviewed in relation to the focus of the study;

1. Concept of the Visual Resources
2. Role of Visual arts in Ghanaian society
3. Visual arts as teaching and learning medium
4. Sustainability of creative works in Ghana

Concept of the Visual Resources

Visual arts are dominant during all life cycle events of Ghanaian society. According to Arthur (2009) the visual arts are the tangible creative works that associate with the human senses. She opines that these types of arts are seen in a form of painting, sculpture and drawing. She adds that, all these artifacts have central idea that communicates to audience in society. According to Doughan (2012), visual arts are the physical objects that are tangible in society. He explains that, those tangible arts include monuments, buildings and landscape that have meaning in the societies in which they are found. He cites an example of the monuments at Mankesim in the Central Region of Ghana showcasing the life of the leaders of the area Odumankoman, Odapagyam and Oson who led the people from Tehiman.

Dzramdo et.al (2013) equally shares that, visual arts play vital role among the Ghanaian societies especially when it comes to the observations of funerals. They discuss that the clothings and their colours that are used during the funeral celebrations display elements of visual arts. Ndah et.al (2021) also support that, the visual arts are the tangible objects found within Ghanaian society. They cite examples in the funerals of the Akan and explain that the posters, costumes, decorations and even the caskets portray the visual arts.

It could therefore be inferred from the assertion of the scholars above that, visual resources are the creative pieces that are visible to human senses in society.

Role of visual arts in Ghanaian society

Ghanaians are so incline to the visual arts as that manifest in the way of life of them; as during their everyday activities visual arts are seen among them. According to Nkansah (2008) visual arts serve as objects of worship and honour. He cites example of stool among the Akan traditional setting and shares that the stool is an artifact that falls under the visual

arts. He explains further that, among the Akan society, the stool is revered and is also worshiped; because it is belief it carries the soul and spirit of the communities in which they are found.

Ndah et al (2021) equally share that the visual arts serve as a medium of communication in Ghanaian society. They opine that the visual objects carry messages to their communities. They gave examples of drawing that are found on drums among the people of Logba in the Volta Region of Ghana and share that they are used to communicate messages to the members.

According to Adu-Agem et al (2013), most of the artifacts fall under the visual arts and are used for their aesthetic effects. They argue that the visual arts are used to beautify society. They further share that even in the midst of the beautification; the arts equally have meaning and significance in the community.

Doughan (2012) as well states that visual arts are good tools when one wants to preserve history and culture. He supports his assertion by stating that the history of the Mankesim people in the Central Region of Ghana are best preserved in the visual arts. He explains that the war Lords of the people of Mankesim are crafted in the area and as soon as those art works are seen, the history of the people in the area are remembered.

Ndah et al (2021) equally discuss that the history and culture of a community is preserved through the visual arts. They cite examples of the Golden Stool and some other artifact among the people of Logba Tota in the Volta Region which preserved the history of the co – existence between the Asante people and their Ewe counterparts.

Adjei (2015) as well argue that visual arts are used during chieftaincy rites among the people of Ghana. He clarifies that, some of the arts are used to adorn chiefs, some as objects of worship and others also serve as object of protection. He continues further that, among the Kona people in the Ashanti Region of Ghana some of the visual arts regalia associated with the chieftaincy are the state sword (Akafuna), the great smock (Batakarekese) umbrellas and palanquin.

Arthur (2009) equally opines that the visual art are used to showcase the identity of a particular society. She gives an example of costume as a theme under the visual arts and explains that, whenever costumes are put on, they show the status of a person in the society as well as the ethnic group that the person comes from.

Visual Resources as teaching and learning medium

Just as the visual arts play their roles in Ghanaian society in general, they are equally useful during the teaching and learning situation.

According to Annkuti and Lodonu (2012), visual arts in teaching and learning help to relate the abstract themes to reality. They share that, in the teaching and learning especially among the lower classes, it is bound on teachers to adopt teaching and learning resources to help the learners perceive their lessons in physical terms. They explain that visual art forms such as painting, drawing, sculpture and observation in nature are used during teaching and learning to make lesson meaningful to the learners.

According to Assenso et al (2020), visual arts in teaching and learning situations help in inculcating among the learners how to appreciate their culture, which is always fused in the creative works They give examples of how visual arts help learners to keep their environment clean as well as conserve the environment. They discuss also that, the inclusion of the visual arts in teaching and learning help to bringing out the creativity among them. In addition, they opine that the visual arts guide to shape the communicative skills of the learners as they are free to interpret these objects in class.

Yeboah, Asante and Opoku Asare (2016) corroborate that, visual arts in teaching and learning help in clarification and demystification of concepts. They argue that the cry all over about fallen standards in education in current days is as a result of many teachers teaching their lessons in abstract form without involvement of visual resources. They state that when visual arts are involved in teaching and learning, it helps to make understanding of lessons easier.

They stress that, the role of visual arts in teaching helps to arouse the interest of the learner since they are free to appreciate and criticize art works.

They further discuss that the artifacts in teaching help in assimilation of ideas as the objects guide them easily to understand lessons taught. They further opine that, after assimilation, the artifacts guide to retain knowledge impacted. They equally agree that, the tangible objects in teaching help to boost the communicative skills of the learners. According to them as well, use of visual arts in teaching saves teaching time; because it takes a little effort for the learners to understand lesson taught.

Sustainability of creative works in Ghana

Creative works are integral part of society, and for that matter must be protected for posterity. According to Dedzoe (2014), the arts help in the holistic training and development of individual; especially children; she therefore ask that conscious efforts should be made to sustain such arts among the people. She suggests that one of the best ways to make the creative arts in society sustainable is to have them recorded on digital platforms for preservation. She states that, once these arts are stored digitally, they would be preserved hence sustained.

Dzansi – Mcpalm (2006) as well shares that arts stand for the cultural beliefs and philosophies of society. So they must be sustainable in society. She states that, one of the means to make the arts sustainable among the people especially the youth is to include their study in the formal system of education. She expresses optimism that once such arts are introduced into the school system, it would arouse interest in their study among students, hence sustaining them.

It could therefore be summed from this review that visual arts are the creative works that are tangible or visible to human senses. And, visual arts play communicative, career, worship and entertainment roles in society. Also, visual arts are used to make lessons so comprehensible during the teaching and learning situation.

It is therefore seen from the authors above that visual arts are vital in teaching and lesson delivery as they impact positively both the teachers and learners.

3. METHODOLOGY

This chapter deals with the general procedures the researcher followed in carrying out the research. It includes the research design and the population of the study. It also covers sampling techniques, description of research instruments, data collection procedure and data analysis.

Research design

The study is qualitative in nature. According to Monik, H, Hutter, I and Bailey, A (2020), qualitative research deals with collection, analyzing and interpreting data by observing people in their natural environment. The researcher blended many techniques to undertake this study. One of the techniques was descriptive techniques for the reason being that she sought to investigate the role of visual arts in teaching and learning at Kyebi Primary School. The following reasons below necessitated the used of the descriptive technique:

- a. It helped to unearth the issues of study based on observation.
- b. It offered the researcher the opportunity to observe the natural relationship that exist in the research variables precisely; the role of visual arts in teaching and learning at Kyebi Basic School.
- c. It provided the platform for the researcher to describe one after the other the roles identified during teaching and learning situations.

A survey technique was equally used in the study especially when it got to distribution of the questionnaire; it helped in reaching out to many respondents quickly and at lesser cost. The questionnaire was used to obtain data relevant to the study.

Observation technique was also employed to enable the researcher see demonstrations of how the visual resources are used generally in and outside classroom in the study area.

Population of the study

Population means a chosen group for administration of a questionnaire (Arthur 2009). The target population of the study includes teachers and students of the Kyebi Primary School. These categories of people were targeted because students come into contact with a lot of visual art materials in and outside the classroom. During their leisure hours as well, they interact with visual objects hence learn some generic skills from the manipulation of these objects. Therefore, they were considered as those who could contribute meaningfully to the topic under study.

The teachers are vital as implementers of policies related to education as well as the curriculum. They teach the creative arts and as well prepare the teaching and learning resources. So, with their vast experience, they cannot be left out when a study is being done on roles of visual arts in the classroom. Since the teachers are experts in the topic under study, they are involved in the study.

Sampling and Sampling procedure

According to Alvi (2016), sampling is the act of choosing a small group of people from a larger group for purposes of research. In view of the assertion above, random sampling technique was used to sample 60 students for the study. This method was adopted because all the students had same characteristics and any one of them could contribute meaningfully to the study.

Purposive sampling method was also used to sample 10 teachers to help in the study. According to Doughan (2012), purposive sampling is the selection of people based on the particular purpose of the study. This method was adopted for the teachers because the researcher had in mind those teachers who teach creative arts as well as those who are inclined in the visual arts related activities in the school and the Kyebi community; and thought they could be of immense help to provide accurate data for the study since they use those arts often.

So, in all 70 respondents were selected using various sampling techniques for the study. The breakdown can be seen on table 1, below:

Table 1: Population and sampling methods for the study

Target population	Accessible population	Sampling method
Teachers	10	Purposive
Students	60	Random

Total population for the study = 70

Data collection instruments

Data was gathered for the study using questionnaire, interviews and observation.

Observation was used because;

1. It gave first-hand experience to the researcher on how the visual arts are used in teaching and learning.
2. It helped to have a feel of such creative works that are under the visual arts. The researcher had a chance of witnessing exhibition of creative works that took place in the school; which offered the researcher the opportunity to ask questions which helped in this study.

Interviews were also used because it afforded the opportunity to the respondents to give details of what are needed for the study.

Questionnaire equally helped in getting information from the respondents as fast as possible and with lesser cost. The questionnaire was made up of eight items covering closed and opened ended types. Names were not permitted on the questionnaire. This was done to maintain anonymity of the respondents hence give them confidence to give information without fear of victimization.

Data collection procedure.

Data was collated from interviews. The researcher also obtained responses from students on the roles the visual arts play during teaching and learning situations.

In all, 30 of the students were interviewed and 30 of them as well responded to the questionnaire. Ten teachers also responded to the interview guide.

The researcher equally deduced from exhibitions she has witnessed in the area and other visual works she had observed and drew conclusions appropriately bearing in mind the focus of the study.

Data Analysis Procedure

The responses from the questionnaire and the interview were analyzed manually and figures brought out. Electronic devices such as mobile phones and digital cameras were used to record and take pictures of some art works; which were played many times and the contents translated into writing.

This chapter has been concluded as the target population was appropriately sampled and information gathered from them was as well analyzed to bring out the needed information for the study.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study sought to discuss the creative works that fall under the visual arts, discuss the role of the visual arts in the teaching and learning at the study area; and also, to outline the ways through which the visual resources could be sustained among the learners in Kyebi Community.

For the 30 students who responded to the questionnaire, 26 of them thus 86.6 % explained the visual resources as the creative works that can be seen. The remaining 4 of them stated that they are the materials that teachers use to teach them in class. This response is represented on a pie chart below:

In identifying some of creative works under the visual resources, 20 of them representing 67% identified painting on wall, drawing and sculpture. The rest also maintained that buildings and their color, blackboard in class and furniture as well as dress worn in class. This response is equally seen on a pie chart below:

As to whether the Visual arts are useful in society, 25 of them stated that they are very relevant. They gave some of their reasons as arts help in worship, help in housing, decorations, record history use for teaching and learning. 5 respondents stated they are not relevant because they are used for shrine purposes. This response is represented on a histogram below:

Those who responded that the arts are relevant explained their stance further and discussed that, the Visual Arts such as whiteboard helps to write, furniture helps them to sit comfortably for academic work. They added that the Teaching Learning Resources used in teaching help them to comprehend the lesson well. In addition, the visual arts help them to be creative as they observe such materials and try to imitate their drawings or composition. As to how the visual arts should be sustained among them, they agreed that visual arts should be made compulsory in their schools and also made examinable.

They stated also that arts festivals should be maintained in schools; where students would be given the opportunity to create their own works for display. They also added that students should be given the chance to be doing art works in their schools when the need be, rather than going outsiders to do them, so that it would give students avenue to practice their creativity. They again agreed that they would always support visual arts in their school.

All the Thirty (30) students interviewed explained that, the creative works that are seen could be referred to as visual arts. They mentioned some of the visual arts resources as paintings, word cards, drawings the sculpture works, furniture they sit on, and the clothings they wear.

They unanimously agreed that the visual arts are very useful in the society. On the use of Visual Arts in teaching and learning, they identified that visual arts help them to write properly, read properly. In addition, the furniture they sit on to write is as a result of visual arts.

They added that the Teaching learning resources that are used to teach them help them to acquire understanding of the lesson faster. In addition, they stated that the charts and objects used to teach them help the teacher to talk less whilst the pictures explain the topics to them. They stated that some of the abstract themes and lessons are made visible and comprehensible by the use of the visual resources.

As to how these arts could be sustained, they explained that they should be made compulsory in schools; there should be arts exhibitions and festivals. They added that should be practical oriented than theory. They stated that they would always support the use of the visual arts in the school because the socio-economic, stating of society depends on the visual arts as household artifacts, school equipment are all products of the visual arts.

Ten (10) teachers were also interviewed and they agreed that, Visual Arts are tangible objects that appeal to the eyes. They mentioned various art works that fall under the Visual Arts as sculpture drawings, furniture and clothing. They stated that Visual Arts are relevant in society; that without the Visual Arts society would be stagnant. As to the role of Visual Arts in teaching and learning, they mentioned that the Teaching learning resources use in teaching, the school building, the school uniforms are all creative works. They added that Visual Arts such as maps, charts and periodicals help to bring abstract themes to reality. Also, furniture and dusters are all Visual Arts that help to deliver lessons properly.

They stated that the Visual Arts in lessons help to learn Ghanaian culture since most of the arts relate to the Ghanaian environment. They also help to bring creativity among teachers and students. As to how to sustain these arts, they shared that, Arts and cultural festivals in schools should be strengthen to help bring out more creative works from students. Also, they stated that it should be made compulsory subjects at all levels of Education in Ghana and also open days and exhibitions in schools should be encouraged so that students' art works would be displayed.

Plate 3: wall paint showing some vegetables

Plate 4: Drawing, showing parts of the human body

Plate 7: Picture of the heads of states of Ghana from 1960- 2022

Plate 8: White board for writing at Kyebi Primary School

Plate 9: Furniture in Kyebi Primary School Classroom

Plate 10: Wall Hung in the Classroom

The others are costume, furniture in class as well as the black/white boards for writing. The building and the architecture in the school environment and the community equally constitute the visual arts. The study also revealed the roles of the visual arts in teaching and learning at the Kyebi Primary School as follows:

5. DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

The visual arts in the form of teaching, learning materials helped to relate the abstract themes to reality thereby enhancing understanding among the learners. Also, the use of the visual objects in teaching helped to involve all the learners in class thereby making them active to contribute to the lesson.

It came clear that the use of the visual arts in the teaching and learning helped to arouse the interest of the learners. Once the interest of the learners is sustained, it makes understanding easier.

The study also revealed that the use of the visual materials in class enhanced retentive memory since it is generally adopted that, when learners see things physically, they remember it faster than hearing about it. (For example, children seeing the parts of the human body on plate 4 and the heads of states of Ghana from the first republic to the fourth republic on plate 7 would make the learners easily remember).

In addition, the visual materials helped to boost the communicative skills of the learners since they appreciate by interpreting these Visual objects during teaching and learning situations.

The study also made it clear that, the visual arts in teaching helped to unearth the creative abilities of the learners as they are challenged to prepare some of these objects themselves.

Also, the use of the visual arts saved teaching time, as the teacher would not have to talk more before the lesson is understood. these findings of the study have therefore confirmed the assertion of Yeboah et al (2016) that visual arts in teaching and learning help learners to understand lessons easily, help to sustain their interest in class, help to explore their creative talents and also help to boost their retentive memories.

The study equally revealed some of the means by which the visual arts could be sustained among the students, as the cultural festivals that are held annually in the basic and second cycle institutions should be strengthen so that the creative works could be showcase to help to sustain the interest of the arts among the learners.

The study made it clear that, exhibitions should be periodically organized on class basis so that works of students could always be put on display.

In addition, practical assignments should be given to students so that once they work on them their interest would be aroused towards the arts.

It came out clear also that visual arts should be included at all levels of educational system. And once that is done it would help to sustain the interest among the learners.

6. SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS

Visual resources form an integral part of Kyebi community. In everyday activities of the members of the community, visual arts play vital role. Visual arts that are seen in form of painting, drawing, sculpture, clothing, buildings and decorations are seen during festivals, worships and during teaching and learning. The major findings of the study are as follows

1. Visual resources in the teaching and learning help to arouse the interest of the learners. Once the interest of the learners is sustained, it makes understanding easier.
2. The use of the visual materials in class enhanced retentive memory since it is generally adopted that, when learners see things physically, they remember it faster than hearing about it. (For example, children seeing the parts of the human body on plate 4 and the heads of states of Ghana from the first republic to the fourth republic on plate 7 would make the learners easily remember).
3. Visual materials helped to boost the communicative skills of the learners since they appreciate by interpreting these Visual objects during teaching and learning situations.
4. Visual arts in teaching helped to unearth the creative abilities of the learners as they are challenged to prepare some of these objects themselves.
5. The use of the visual arts saved teaching time, as the teacher would not have to talk more before the lesson is understood. these findings of the study have therefore confirmed the assertion of Yeboah et al (2016) that visual arts in teaching and learning help learners to understand lessons easily, help to sustain their interest in class, help to explore their creative talents and also help to boost their retentive memories.

7. CONCLUSION

It has been revealed that, visual arts are the creative works that appeal to the eyes of the viewers. And that some of the works that could be referred to as visual arts are paintings, drawings, moldings, carvings not forgetting buildings and clothing in the community. The study equally made it clear that, Visual Arts help learners to gain understanding of concepts easily during teaching and learning. Also, they help to sustain the interest of the learners. In addition; they help to relate the abstract objects to reality. Besides, they help to enhance retentive memory among learners. The study revealed also that the use of the visual materials in class help to keep the students so active.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study has put forward the following recommendations for consideration.

1. The policy makers and curriculum planners in Ghana through Sekyere Central Education directorate should introduce the visual arts at all levels of Education so that learners could harvest all the benefits that these arts offer.
2. The use of teaching and learning materials (teaching resources) in teaching should be strengthened especially in all Kyebi Schools so that it would save teaching time but help learners internalize understanding of concepts.
3. Practical based assignments should be employed in class so that the creative abilities of learners could be sharpen.
4. Cultural festivals in the first and second cycle instructions in Ghana should be encouraged so that, more of learner's creative works could be showcased.

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